

THE IMPACT OF TRAINING SET SELECTION ON CRATER COUNTING IN DEEP LEARNING

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Introduction:

Impact cratering is the most ubiquitous geological process in the Solar System. Crater counting provides information about the relative age of a planetary surface, the planet's bombardment history, and erosion rates.

The high spatial resolution of today's flown imaging orbiters can make craters visible down into the 10 m range. While the major geological lunar periods are defined by the large impact events, it is the smaller impacts which due to their much shorter lifetime are interesting for the recent lunar history and allow one to shed light on the physics of the degradation processes involved. Small lunar impact craters show diverse morphological characteristics. These craters can be used as crucial indicators for understanding surface modification processes, such as regolith thickness distribution. While automated crater detection has seen remarkable progress, classification of small crater morphotypes remains underexplored, particularly due to inherent class imbalances in existing datasets. Due to the power law of the crater size scaling, the traditional methods of human-based crater counting is no longer feasible. There is no shortage of studies in the literature which use automated crater detection algorithms to construct the desired crater distribution functions (see e.g.[1]).

Object recognition is defined as the ability to assign labels to particular objects, ranging from precise labels ("identification") to course labels ("categorization"). The difficulties in automatic crater recognition arise from the fact that the multi-scale characteristics of impact cratering combined with the erosional processes create dense overlapping structural morphologies which have to be associated with individual impact events. Only in the case when a crater is formed on a fresh surface do we have the ideal case which when imaged would lead to the perfect image we would like to have for a clear classification.

As we deal primarily with mature planetary surfaces, we face the issue of how to separate the power of the detection efficiency of an algorithm itself from the impact which the choice of the training set has on the results generated with it. Defining what a "good" training set means is by itself already a difficult problem. This problem becomes already apparent when we try to benchmark the detection efficiency of an "ideal observer", often taken as a human expert (e.g. geomorphologist) and assume that such a person defines the "gold standard". Robbins et al. (2014) [2] found that the dispersion among experts in the number of craters identified in different size bins to vary anywhere from 10% to 35%.

Many studies have rated different algorithms against each other on a given dataset but do not investigate the choice of the training data on the overall crater detection efficiency. This issue becomes particularly important when we are dealing with one class object detection problems, where there is only one class of object to be found on a mature cratered surface.

Purpose of study:

The goal of this work is to investigate how the training set can influence the quoted detection efficiency of one particular single state-of-the art object detector.

Choosing the detector:

Automatic impact crater detection methods can be classified into digital image processing techniques and deep-learning-based methods. Image processing detection methods have mainly relied on edge detection methods, morphology-based feature extraction and traditional machine learning methods, etc. These methods extract the circular, ring-like features of craters from orbiter images or digital elevation models. The effectiveness of these approaches deteriorate when craters lose their clear boundaries. and the images are affected by shadows, noise and other factors, leading to a limited recognition accuracy. In recognizing the very small craters, many of these algorithms have problems from distinguishing craters from boulders [see e.g. [3]. This is particularly a problem in the slope regions of bigger craters or around boulder fields.

Deep-learning algorithms are divided into two-stage detection and one-stage detection algorithms. Two-stage detection networks are represented by R-CNN, Faster RCNN, Sparse R-CNN, etc., which need to generate candidate regions first, then perform object category prediction and more accurate bounding box regression on the investigated regions. On the other side, one-stage detection algorithms directly predict the location and category of the target without pre-generating the candidate region. Compared to two-stage algorithms, one-stage object detection algorithms are simpler and faster. As a result, numerous networks using one-stage detection algorithms for the recognition of planetary surface impact craters have emerged, such as CraterNet, AE-TransUNet, DeepMoon, YOLO-Crater, and HRFPNet to name only a few. The above studies have made progress in automatic impact crater detection, but there remains several significant challenges.

From the many possible detector choices, we have chosen YOLOX as our detector. YOLOX was

proposed by Ge et al. [4]. It fully learns and borrows from the hot anchorless detection, advanced label assignment strategy and end-to-end detector in the field of target detection. The addition of an anchorless mechanism to YOLOX has the advantage that it significantly reduces the parameters of the network and also makes the recognition accuracy and detection speed of YOLOX faster. Responsible for this was the addition of four components: Decoupled Head, Data Augmentation, Free Anchor, and SimOTA sample. Numerous studies have shown that the performance of anchorless detectors can be comparable to that of anchored detectors. In addition, the anchorless mechanism makes the training and decoding phases of the detectors simpler.

Data utilized and generation of training sets:

For this study we have chosen five lunar locations: Apollo 17, Jules Vernes, Ranger 6, Ranger 8 and a region in Mare Humorum. For each of these regions we have identified four 8-bit TIFF LRO-NAC images having a range of incidence angles (between 55° and 75°) and different solar azimuth angles. The calibrated images were projected and scaled to 0.5 m per pixel using ISIS, and cropped to precisely the same area, to within just a few pixels in x and y. The cropped images are then divided into 4-12 sub-images dependent on the size of the regions used for easier handling (see Fig.1).

Figure 1: Process of generating the crater data-base for this study: After the location selection, four NAC images taken under very different illumination conditions are chosen, then cropped and sampled to a resolution of 0.5m. The investigated region is subdivided into four parts. A single part of the investigated region is shown in B1-B3. From each of the four NAC images crater lists were generated by traditional imaging

techniques. Candidate craters were selected based on various criteria to form a master training list to arrive at images as B3, where the best candidates are shown in the green color. A1 shows an example of the ground truth data for a small 550x550 sub-image of a part of the NAC section. A2 shows the YOLOX identified craters on the same image.

Crater identification was done independently by traditional image processing detection methods by both authors (for details, see e.g. Cadogan, 2024 [5]) on all the NAC images used. For each NAC image of the five lunar locations, tables were produced with the crater locations given as circles, along with their radii. For each identified crater in the five regions, we counted how many times the crater could be identified under the four different imaging conditions (see Fig. 2). Additionally, a freshness and contrast level was defined for each crater.

We will report in this study how various selection criteria impact the performance of the YOLOX detector for identifying different crater classes.

Figure 2: Four of the same sections of an NAC image M182566427R taken under four different illumination conditions showing the crater locations determined by traditional imaging methods.

References:

- [1] Heyer, T., et al., (2023) *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 231, July 2023, 105687. [2] Robbins, S.J., et al., (2014) *Icarus*, 234 (2014) 109–131. [3] Mall, U., et al., (2023) *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 10 art. 1176325. [4] Ge, Z., et al., (2021) *arXiv preprint arXiv: 2107.08430* (2021). [5] Cadogan, P., (2024) *Icarus*, Volume 408, 2024, 115796.